

strong aya

A new, interdisciplinary, multi-stakeholder European network to improve healthcare services, research and outcomes for Adolescents and Young Adults with cancer.

The future of cancer therapy

YOUTH
CANCER
EUROPE

Deliverable Report

WP2 – Governance, data security and ethics

Deliverable D2.6

First report on stakeholder engagement focused on patient-centered and patient-informed ethical guidance

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Description:

First report on stakeholder engagement focused on patient-centered and patient-informed ethical guidance

Publishable summary (max ½ page)

This report provides a targeted literature review of patient involvement practices and patient involvement evaluation practices focused on the field of AYA cancer research. In recent years, efforts to involve patients in AYA research have been introduced within the AYA population, though the number of initiatives is still relatively small. Despite the widespread calls for involvement practices, implementation, monitoring and evaluation practices for AYA participation are lacking in many European countries. There are currently no European standards for involvement practices with AYAs with lived experience of cancer: context-dependent policies and best practices should be developed. This report offers a preliminary mapping of the type of patient involvement practices that are part of the STRONG AYA project, showing examples of ‘consent’, ‘consultation’ and ‘cooperation’ practices. The report also discusses the topic of evaluation frameworks for patient involvement in relation to STRONG AYA’s involvement efforts. A wide variety of frameworks and guidelines exist in academic and professional literature, with differing approaches and focus. Recently, two guidelines specifically centered on improving patient involvement in AYA research have been published. The report ends with recommendations for improving evaluation frameworks for patient involvement in the context of research projects such as STRONG AYA.

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2 Definitions

STRONG AYA consortium members are referred to as following within this text:

1. **NKI-AVL** – Stichting het Nederlands Kanker Instituut – Antoni van Leeuwenhoek Ziekenhuis (NL)
2. **YCE** – Youth Cancer Europe (RO)
3. **INT** – Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori (IT)
4. **FFUND** – FFUND BV (NL)
5. **CLB** – Centre de Lutte Contre le Cancer Leon Berard (FR)
6. **ECO** – European Cancer Organisation (BE)
7. **UNIMAAS** – Universiteit Maastricht (NL)
8. **IKNL** – Stichting Integraal Kankercentrum Nederland (NL)
9. **EORTC** – European Organisation for Research and Treatment of Cancer AISBL (BE)
10. **IGR** – Institut Gustave Roussy (FR)
11. **MSCNRIO** – Narodowy Instytut Onkologii im. Marii Skłodowskiej-Curie – Państwowy Instytut Badawczy (Marie Skłodowska-Curie National Research Institute of Oncology) (PL)
12. **UOM** – University of Manchester (UK)
13. **UOL** – University of Leeds (UK)
14. **LTHT** – Leeds Teaching Hospitals National Health Service Trust (UL)
15. **SOUTHAMPTON** – University of Southampton (UK)

- **Grant Agreement** (including its annexes and amendments): the agreement signed between the beneficiaries of the HORIZON Research and Innovations Actions (hereafter referred to as Horizon) and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (hereafter referred to as HADEA) for the undertaking of the STRONG AYA project (Grant Agreement no. 101057482).
- **Beneficiary**: Signatories of the Grant Agreement
- **Associated Partner**: Entities which participate in the action but without the right to charge costs or claim contributions.
- **Project**: the sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
- **Consortium**: the STRONG AYA consortium, including all the aforementioned partners.
- **Consortium Agreement**: The agreement made between STRONG AYA members for the implementation and execution of the action outlined in the Grant Agreement. The agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to HADEA on behalf of the European Union, and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.

3 Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Meaning
HCP	Health Care Provider
PRO	Patient Reported Outcome
PROM	Patient Reported Outcome Measure
COS	Core Outcome Set
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Lead(s)
WP1	Work Package 1 (Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer & data collection)
WP2	Work Package 2 (Governance, Data Security and Ethics)
WP3	Work Package 3 (Infrastructure and Interoperability)
WP4	Work Package 4 (Operation of STRONG AYA ecosystems, stakeholder and patient involvement, dissemination, exploitation, communication)
WP5	Work Package 5 (Scientific coordination and project management)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OA	Open Access
PAB	Patient Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
HADEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
SC	Steering Committee
MT	Management Team

4 Introduction

4.1 Project background

Cancer at adolescent and young adult (AYA) age (15-39 at primary diagnosis) is rare. However, this rarity does not reflect the significant personal and societal costs of cancer in this population, as reflected in the potential years of life lost or saved, the decreased productivity and quality-of-life due to the impact of the disease during formative years, and the long-term complications or disabilities¹. AYAs with cancer form a unique group; they face age-specific issues (e.g. Infertility, unemployment, financial problems) and decreased quality of life due to cancer and its treatment. Unlike dedicated healthcare and trials for paediatric cancer patients, AYA-specific healthcare services are scarce and vary across Europe. AYAs who are at the core of society and the economy need access to age-appropriate and high-quality healthcare.

The STRONG-AYA project aims to tackle the underrepresentation of AYA's experiences and outcomes when navigating the healthcare system and in clinical care by developing national infrastructures for outcome data management and clinical decision-making within a pan-European ecosystem and establishing communication feedback for AYAs with cancer and the healthcare systems. This will be key to improving healthcare services, research, outcomes and policies for AYAs and to ultimately better cancer care for this patient group. The project brings together an international multi-disciplinary consortium (academic/research, clinical, stakeholder and patient organisations) across seven European countries.

Building on previous initiatives, a STRONG-AYA data ecosystem will be set up for value-based care, research and policy for AYA with cancer by:

1. **Developing a Core Outcome Set (COS)** specifically for AYAs with cancer, via a participative consensus process defining most important aspects for those directly affected by AYA cancer, including patients and healthcare professionals.
2. **Implementing the COS across several national European healthcare systems.** Data will be collected at local level and will then be included in a data integration platform. An overall ecosystem framework for data analytics and output will be created supporting federated analyses and the creation of reports across clinical and patient-reported data and making national repositories of (patient-reported) health data, available to individual patients, patient organisations, regulatory authorities, as well as the patients' health care providers to inform clinical decision-making. The five resulting **national ecosystems** will be connected to each other into **the pan-European ecosystem** using a federated approach also utilizing the overall ecosystem framework.
3. **Disseminating the COS to a wide range of local as well as pan-European stakeholders,** in particular by developing analytical tools to process and present patient outcome data and establish feedback loops that inform patients and clinicians.

Implementing these project objectives are five work packages within the STRONG-AYA project:

- WP1: Development Core Outcome Set AYA with cancer and Data Collection (Lead: SOUTHAMPTON)
- WP2: Governance, Data Security and Ethics (Lead: EORTC)
- WP3: Infrastructure and Interoperability (Lead: UNIMAAS)
- WP4: Operation of STRONG-AYA ecosystems, Stakeholder and Patient involvement, Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication (Lead: E.C.O.)

¹ Stoneham SJ. AYA survivorship: The next challenge. Cancer 2020; 126: 2116-2119.

- WP5: Scientific Coordination and Project Management (Lead: NKI)

STRONG-AYA will enable AYA care and research to benefit from collection and pooling of patient-centered data and collaboration among all stakeholders: patients, healthcare professionals, scientists, and policymakers. More widely, the project will leverage the network of interested organisations and networks established under STRONG-AYA for long-term strengthened promotion of the necessary implementation of specialist AYA cancer services across Europe. This will ultimately bring novel insights into AYA cancer care, research and policy, contributing to the long-term improvement of outcomes for people with AYA cancer.

4.2 Deliverable introduction

The report focuses on reviewing patient involvement and evaluation practices specifically within AYA (Adolescent and Young Adult) cancer research. The report provides a **targeted literature review on patient involvement and involvement evaluation practices** with special attention to AYA (Adolescent and Young Adult) cancer research.

Key take away points:

- Although efforts to involve patients in AYA research have begun, the number of such initiatives remains relatively small.
- No standardized practices exist in Europe for involving AYAs with lived experience of cancer, highlighting the need for context-specific policies and best practices.
- A wide range of evaluation frameworks and guidelines for patient involvement are available in the literature, each with different approaches and focuses.
- Two guidelines aimed at improving patient involvement specifically in AYA research have been recently published.

Preliminary Mapping of Involvement Practices: The report maps out the types of patient involvement practices within the STRONG AYA project, categorizing them into 'consent,' 'consultation,' and 'cooperation' practices.

Recommendations for Evaluation Improvement: The report concludes with suggestions for enhancing evaluation frameworks for patient involvement in research projects like STRONG AYA.

5 Mapping patient involvement practices in STRONG AYA

5.1 Background to this report

This report builds on the first STRONG AYA Stakeholder Forum Meeting on 27 September 2023: 'Caught in the Middle: Identifying Gaps for Adolescents and Young Adults with Cancer'. This Stakeholder Forum meeting brought together 70 participants (including healthcare professionals, policy makers and patient representatives) to provide feedback on the consortium's ongoing activities and to bring AYA Community's attention to the project. In engaging with stakeholders during this event, an additional aim was to signal emerging issues that need further elucidation and examination during the development of STRONG AYA. During the event, the issue of patient involvement surfaced as a returning topic of conversation. In tandem, in 2023, the STRONG AYA Ethics and Regulatory advisory board (ERAB), also asked to clarify STRONG AYA's approach to patient involvement. The current report jointly responds to these demands for clarification and provides a mapping of ongoing efforts within STRONG AYA to realise different forms of patient involvement. Another aim is to summarise relevant literature that can help to suitably evaluate AYA patient involvement practices. As the STRONG AYA consortium is currently developing, this report will not comprehensively

evaluate patient involvement but will conclude with pointers for strengthening the evaluation of patient involvement during the further course of the project as well as future research development.

5.1.1 STRONG AYA's aims for patient involvement as part of Horizon Europe

From its inception, STRONG AYA underwrites the importance of patient involvement in (data-intensive) health research. STRONG AYA's attention to involvement builds on decades of emerging patient involvement and patient activism in Europe, which have led to the institutionalization and professionalization of patient involvement practices in European research projects, including in HORIZON EUROPE.² Patient involvement has been suggested as a way to improve the effectiveness, sustainability, and quality of medical innovations, to expand patient choice, democratize healthcare decision-making, emancipate patients, and promote fairness and justice in medicine.³ Definitions of patient involvement, engagement or participation vary widely.⁴ A basic definition is “an activity that is done ‘with’ or ‘by’ patients or members of the public rather than ‘to’, ‘about’ or ‘for’ them.”⁵ Many different kinds of involvement practices proliferate: from informing patients about research and consulting with patients by means of questionnaires, to co-designing research design and tools and actively seeking representation by patients on governance bodies.⁶ This variation in types of involvement is also expressed by an expanding involvement vocabulary, such as ‘patient & public involvement’ (PPI), ‘public involvement and engagement’ (PI&E) ‘public engagement’ (PE), ‘patient engagement in research’ (PER), ‘patient partners in research’ (PPR), ‘patient engagement in research’ (PEIR), ‘patient research partner engagement’ (PRPE) and participatory design (PD).

STRONG AYA draws on extensive experience and expertise by our consortium members in the domain of patient involvement, spearheaded by the core expertise of The European Cancer Organization (ECO) and Youth Cancer Europe (YCE). Within the STRONG AYA consortium, ECO takes the lead on stakeholder involvement activities. ECO also has experience working on patient involvement activities, including through its Patient Advisory Committee and role in other EU-funded projects - in that regard, ECO contributed to a very recent handbook on the topic. YCE is leading a consortium-specific STRONG-AYA Patient Advisory Board (PAB), which is responsible for co-creating platforms for patient engagement and co-

² The HORIZON EUROPE funding scheme has underlined the importance of civil society participation in “co-designing and co-creating responsible research and innovation agendas and contents, promoting science education, making scientific knowledge publicly accessible, and facilitating participation by citizens and civil society organisations in its activities.” Regulations. Establishing Horizon Europe – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, laying down its rules for participation and dissemination, and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1290/2013 and (EU) No 1291/2013. (2021). *Official Journal of the European Union*, 170, 51.

³ For an overview of envisioned effects of patient involvement, see for example Prainsack, B. (2017). *Personalized Medicine: Empowered Patients in the 21st Century?* NYU Press. Madden, M., & Speed, E. (2017). *Beware Zombies and Unicorns: Toward Critical Patient and Public Involvement in Health Research in a Neoliberal Context.* *Frontiers in Sociology*, 2.

⁴ Baines et al. (2022) found 133 terms to describe forms of involvement, with ‘user-centred design’, ‘participatory design’ and ‘codesign’ most commonly used. Baines, R., Bradwell, H., Edwards, K., Stevens, S., Prime, S., Treddinick-Rowe, J., Sibley, M., & Chatterjee, A. (2022). Meaningful patient and public involvement in digital health innovation, implementation and evaluation: A systematic review. *Health Expectations*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.13506>. Castro, E. M., Van Regenmortel, T., Vanhaecht, K., Sermeus, W., & Van Hecke, A. (2016). Patient empowerment, patient participation and patient-centeredness in hospital care: A concept analysis based on a literature review. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 99(12), 1923–1939. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2016.07.026>

⁵ Ocloo, J., & Matthews, R. (2016). From tokenism to empowerment: Progressing patient and public involvement in healthcare improvement. *BMJ Quality & Safety*, 25(8), 626–632. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjqs-2015-004839>. Additionally, a useful distinction has been made between individual and collective patient participation: “Individual patient participation revolves around a patients’ rights and opportunities to influence and engage in decision making about their care through a dialogue attuned to a patient’s preferences, potential and a combination of his experiential and the professional’s expert knowledge. Collective patient participation is the contribution of patients or their representing organizations in shaping health and social care services by means of active involvement in a range of activities at the individual, organizational and policy level that combine experiential and professional knowledge.” Castro, E. M., Van Regenmortel, T., Vanhaecht, K., Sermeus, W., & Van Hecke, A. (2016). Patient empowerment, patient participation and patient-centeredness in hospital care: A concept analysis based on a literature review. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 99(12), 1923–1939. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2016.07.026>.

⁶ Ocloo, J., & Matthews, R. (2016). From tokenism to empowerment: Progressing patient and public involvement in healthcare improvement. *BMJ Quality & Safety*, 25(8), 626–632. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjqs-2015-004839>.

designing materials related to the project and its outputs for the AYAs with lived experience of cancer. In its collaborative setup, STRONG AYA allows other consortium members to also bring in their expertise with engaging patients developed in their local organizations, including, for example research and guidelines on AYA patient involvement strategies developed by researchers at the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI).⁷

In its involvement efforts, STRONG AYA takes heed of recent discussions on how to successfully realize patient involvement with end-users, patients and patient organizations. The consortium is aware that patient involvement practices are often limited and imperfect, as evidenced by the continuous rally of patient organizations for more and better involvement endeavours and better involvement evaluation practices.⁸ The European Patient Forum has emphasized, for example (in a response to Horizon Europe’s remarks about civil society participation) that involvement needs to be “meaningful” (“systematic, structured, non-tokenistic and appropriately resourced”) and should take place during all stages of a research project, from conceptualization to evaluation.⁹ Being mindful of these ongoing calls for improving involvement practices, this report also includes recommendations towards the further development of STRONG AYA, as well as future data-intensive AYA research.

5.1.2 STRONG AYA and European ethical principles for digital health

The development of STRONG-AYA tools is directed by the imperative of interpreting and following ethical principles that are centred on the interests and values of patients. The European Ethical Principles for Digital Health¹⁰ provide the foundation that research within the STRONG-AYA consortium builds upon, ensuring that the core principles are iterated and reflected in the development federated learning ecosystem, and that the iteration of these core principles also reflects the interests and values of the AYA patient groups, as evidenced by stakeholder consultation and engagement. This will include working to try and meet the following ethical desiderata:

Base data-intensive STRONG AYA tools on humanistic values

1. Research and tools developed in STRONG AYA complement and optimize face-to-face healthcare.
2. Patients are informed about the benefits and limits of tools developed in STRONG AYA .
3. Patients are informed about the functioning of tools developed in STRONG AYA and can customize interactions with them.
4. When artificial intelligence is used, all reasonable efforts are made to make it explainable and without discriminatory bias, which also promotes the long-term sustainability of STRONG AYA.

⁷ Van Ham, C. R., Burgers, V. W. G., Sleeman, S. H. E., Dickhout, A., Harthoorn, N. C. G. L., Manten-Horst, E., van Eenbergen, M. C., & Husson, O. (2022). A qualitative study on the involvement of adolescents and young adults (AYAs) with cancer during multiple research phases: “Plan, structure, and discuss.” *Research Involvement and Engagement*, 8(1), 30. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40900-022-00362-w>. Burgers, V. W. G., Dickhout, A., Harthoorn, N. C. G. L., Frissen, S. A. M. M., Noordhoek, M. J., Franssen, S. A., Reuvers, M. J. P., van der Graaf, W. T. A., & Husson, O. (2023). Involving adolescents and young adults (AYA) with an uncertain or poor cancer prognosis as research partners. *Acta Oncologica*, 62(8), 961–968. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0284186X.2023.2238554>

⁸ Matthews, R., Kaur, M., French, C., Baker, A., & Reed, J. (2019). How helpful are Patient and Public Involvement strategic documents—Results of a framework analysis using 4Pi National Involvement Standards. *Research Involvement and Engagement*, 5(1), 31. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40900-019-0164-0>. Greenhalgh, T., Hinton, L., Finlay, T., Macfarlane, A., Fahy, N., Clyde, B., & Chant, A. (2019). Frameworks for supporting patient and public involvement in research: Systematic review and co-design pilot. *Health Expectations*, 22(4), 785–801. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.12888>

⁹ <https://www.eu-patient.eu/news/latest-epf-news/2018/horizon-europe-must-invest-more-in-health-to-support-high-quality-accessible-and-equitable-health-systems/>. This document also refers to the “Value+ Indicators for Meaningful Patient Involvement” in Winder, E. (2009). The Value+ Toolkit. For Patients organisations on meaningful patient involvement. European Patient’s Forum. <https://www.eu-patient.eu/globalassets/projects/valueplus/value-toolkit.pdf>

¹⁰ *European Ethical principles for digital health*. (n.d.). France 22. French presidency of the council of the European Union. Retrieved August 26, 2024, from https://sante.gouv.fr/IMG/pdf/220131_european_ethical_principles_for_digital_health_fr_eng.pdf.

Enable patients to manage their data used in the STRONG AYA tools.

5. Patients are actively involved in shaping the development and governance of STRONG AYA research and tool realization.
6. Patients can easily and reliably retrieve their health data in a commonly used format.
7. Patients can easily access information on how their health data have been or may be accessed and for which purpose.
8. Patients can easily and reliably grant access to their health data and exercise their rights.

Make STRONG AYA tools inclusive

9. Digital Health services developed in STRONG AYA are accessible by all, including by people with disabilities or low levels of (digital & health) literacy.
10. STRONG AYA tools are intuitive and easy to use.
11. Patients have access to training that helps them to use and understand digital health tools.
12. STRONG AYA tools are implemented in care routines that include support through human communication when needed.
13. Strong AYA is accessible and welcoming to new consortium partners and organizations in future.

5.1.3 Scope of this report

This report aims to provide an initial analysis of how patient involvement practices in STRONG AYA could be suitably measured, monitored and evaluated. To do so, the report provides a targeted literature review of patient involvement practices and patient involvement evaluation practices in AYA cancer research, as well as a preliminary exploration of the type of patient involvement practices that are part of the STRONG AYA project. This is only a partial mapping of STRONG AYA’s ongoing (and continuously evolving) efforts to realize various forms of patient involvement in the emerging data-intensive health research during the consortium timeframe (2021 – 2026). Some elements of STRONG AYA’s patient ‘involvement’ or ‘participation’ are outside the scope of this report. STRONG AYA is a pre-eminently ‘patient-centred’ research consortium: part of its aim is to create a ‘core outcome set’ (COS), involving patients, which also includes ‘patient-reported outcome measures’ (PROMs) and to create an interface through which patients can enter patient-reported outcomes data, learn from it and use it in their own care. This report will not discuss patient-reported data per se as a form of patient involvement and is focused instead on patients’ involvement with the various activities of the STRONG AYA research consortium, including governance of the consortium itself, data gathering and processing, research communication, patient recruitment, etc.¹¹

6 Targeted literature review: Practicing and evaluating patient involvement in AYA cancer research

For this report the authors conducted a “targeted literature review,” i.e. a non-systematic review of the literature that is meant to be an informative and in-depth review of literature, rather than an all-encompassing systematic review. Medline and Embase databases were searched for recent literature on patient involvement in AYA cancer research and systematic reviews of patient involvement studies, particularly the evaluation of patient involvement practices. Based on articles found through database

¹¹ In recent discussions, efforts to mobilize patients to collect health-related data have been framed as a form of patient participation, though researchers have pointed out that ‘participation’ does not adequately describe the role of patients in health data provision. Beier, K., Schweda, M., & Schicktanz, S. (2019). Taking patient involvement seriously: A critical ethical analysis of participatory approaches in data-intensive medical research. *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, 19(1), 90. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-019-0799-7>

research, backward and forward snowballing approaches were used to create the final targeted literature review.

6.1 Patient involvement in AYA cancer research

In recent years, efforts to involve patients in AYA research have been introduced within the AYA population, though the number of initiatives is still relatively small. Some examples of involvement efforts with AYA patients include the development of a survey of patients and a toolkit for patient involvement (UK),¹² the establishment of an AYA youth panel (Denmark),¹³ co-creation with the development of a smartphone app for AYA's (Denmark),¹⁴ establishment of 'AYA dream teams' for consultation and involvement practices (the Netherlands),¹⁵ AYA peer visits as a research method,¹⁶ as and co-creation in the development of a mobile application (the Netherlands).¹⁷

Some researchers have remarked that engaging adolescents and young adults with lived experience in cancer research is particularly fitting, as they have been found to lean towards being more autonomous, taking control, and actively participating in their own care journey compared to older age groups.¹⁸ Other research has pointed to differing attitudes towards patient engagement between various AYA age groups. Within the adolescent age group (10 – 20 years old), patients value their healthcare provider's support of their independence more than practices of patient engagement.¹⁹ Conversely, the adult cancer literature suggests that patient engagement is associated with improved quality of care and improved experience of care.²⁰ People with lived experience also differ in their opinion about which phases of research are suitable for AYA involvement. A 2022 study showed that both researchers and AYAs felt positive about involvement in six phases (identify and prioritize topics, develop study design, disseminate information, implement, and

¹² Taylor, R. M., Whelan, J. S., Gibson, F., Morgan, S., Fern, L. A., Aslam, N., Barber, J., Feltbower, R., Fox, Z., Hooker, L., Lea, S., Lerner, M., Martins, A., Moran, T., Morris, S., O'Hara, C., Patel, N., Pearce, S., Raine, R., ... Core Consumer Group (CCG) and National Cancer Research Institute Teenage and Young Adult Clinical Studies Group (NCRI TYA CSG). (2018). Involving young people in BRIGHTLIGHT from study inception to secondary data analysis: Insights from 10 years of user involvement. *Research Involvement and Engagement*, 4(1), 50. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40900-018-0135-x>.

¹³ Pappot, H., Meier, S. K., Hjerding, M., Pii, K., & Hanghøj, S. (2023). Research involvement and engagement of adolescent and young adults in a cancer trajectory: A 5-year experience from a patient support facility at a university hospital. *Research Involvement and Engagement*, 9(1), 56. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40900-023-00464-z>.

¹⁴ Elsbernd, A., Hjerding, M., Visler, C., Hjalgrim, L. L., Niemann, C. U., Boisen, K. A., Jakobsen, J., & Pappot, H. (2018). Using Cocreation in the Process of Designing a Smartphone App for Adolescents and Young Adults With Cancer: Prototype Development Study. *JMIR Formative Research*, 2(2), e9842. <https://doi.org/10.2196/formative.9842>

¹⁵ Vandekerckhove P, De Mul M, De Groot L, Elzevier HW, Fabels B, Haj Mohammad S, et al. Lessons for employing participatory design when developing care for young people with cancer: a qualitative multiple- case study. *J Adolesc Young Adult Oncol*. 2021;10(4):404–17.

¹⁶ "Peer Visit as Research Method in EU-CAYAS-NET. Description of Methodology –Final draftDeveloped under Task 4.2 in Work Package 4: AYA Care." 2024. *European Network of Youth Cancer Survivors (EU-CAYAS-NET)*, April. <https://osf.io/https://osf.io/apgm5>.

¹⁷ Sleeman, S. H. E., Reuvers, M. J. P., Manten-Horst, E., Verhees, B., Patterson, P., Janssen, S. H. M., & Husson, O. (2022). 'Let Me Know If There's Anything I Can Do for You', the Development of a Mobile Application for Adolescents and Young Adults (AYAs) with Cancer and Their Loved Ones to Reconnect after Diagnosis. *Cancers*, 14(5), Article 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers14051178>.

¹⁸ Belpame N, Kars MC, Beeckman D, Decoene E, Quaghebeur M, Van Hecke A, et al. "The AYA Director": a synthesizing concept to understand psycho- social experiences of adolescents and young adults with cancer. *Cancer Nurs*. 2016;39(4):292–302.

¹⁹ Siembida, E. J., Kadan-Lottick, N. S., Moss, K., & Bellizzi, K. M. (2018). Adolescent cancer patients' perceived quality of cancer care: The roles of patient engagement and supporting independence. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 101(9), 1683–1689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2018.04.002>.

²⁰ Hibbard, J. H., & Greene, J. (2013). What The Evidence Shows About Patient Activation: Better Health Outcomes And Care Experiences; Fewer Data On Costs. *Health Affairs*, 32(2), 207–214. <https://doi.org/10.1377/hlthaff.2012.1061>.

evaluate), but overall, not interested in involvement in the phases of formulating research questions, conducting research, and analysing and interpreting results.²¹

Despite the widespread calls for involvement practices, implementation, monitoring and evaluation practices for AYA participation are lacking in many European countries. In 2019, a European Collaborative Workshop on the topic of Patient and Parent Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) in AYA cancer research concluded that there are currently no European standards for involvement practices with AYAs with lived experience and advocated for more collaboration between PPIE interested parties to develop adaptive approaches that fit with the nature of AYA cancer research in different European countries.²² A 2023 Europe-wide survey on PPIE practices in AYA research found that healthcare professionals and patients particularly indicated low levels of involvement in the early stages of research.²³ Moreover, this study found that patients are often not aware of the possibilities of being involved and even lack awareness about the use of their medical/clinical information in further/secondary research.²⁴ In turn, two recent studies, the BRIGHTLIGHT study in the UK (Taylor 2018) and a study by Burgers et al. (2023), demonstrate pioneering attempts to involve AYA patients at various stages of the research process. The BRIGHTLIGHT study in the UK conducted a wide range of AYA-onset cancer PPIE practices, including involvement of patients as "co-researchers, consultants and collaborators" in study design, implementation, interpretation and dissemination of results.²⁵ Burgers et al. (2023) realised involvement of AYA patients - invited as "research partners" - at all stages of the research cycle and provide evidence that forms of involvement can also be realized at early research stages, with patients taking the role of practical support, listeners, co-thinkers, advisors, partners or decision-makers.²⁶ In this study, patients helped to refine information letters and emails, to improve interview guides (with more relevant and less distressing questions), and to better interpret findings from interviews. Beyond improving AYA research and care more generally through involvement, this study also found individual benefits of patient participation: taking part in research tasks also affected feelings of self-

²¹ van Ham, C. R., Burgers, V. W. G., Sleeman, S. H. E., Dickhout, A., Harthoorn, N. C. G. L., Manten-Horst, E., van Eenbergen, M. C., & Husson, O. (2022). A qualitative study on the involvement of adolescents and young adults (AYAs) with cancer during multiple research phases: "Plan, structure, and discuss." *Research Involvement and Engagement*, 8(1), 30. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40900-022-00362-w>.

²² Polanco, A., Al-Saadi, R., Tugnait, S., Scobie, N., & Pritchard-Jones, K. (2022). Setting international standards for patient and parent involvement and engagement in childhood, adolescent and young adult cancer research: A report from a European Collaborative Workshop. *Cancer Reports*, 5(6), e1523. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cnr2.1523>.

²³ Weiler-Wichtl, L. J., Leiss, U., Gojo, J., Kienesberger, A., Hansl, R., Hopfgartner, M., & Schneider, C. (2023). Good to know – This is PPIE! Development of a training tool for public and patient involvement and engagement in pediatric oncological research. *Cancer Reports*, 6(6), e1835. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cnr2.1835>.

²⁴ Weiler-Wichtl, L. J., Leiss, U., Gojo, J., Kienesberger, A., Hansl, R., Hopfgartner, M., & Schneider, C. (2023). Good to know – This is PPIE! Development of a training tool for public and patient involvement and engagement in pediatric oncological research. *Cancer Reports*, 6(6), e1835. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cnr2.1835>.

²⁵ Taylor RM, Lobel B, Thompson K, Onashile A, Croasdale M, Hall N, Gibson F, Martins A, Wright D, Morgan S, Whelan JS, Fern LA. BRIGHTLIGHT researchers as 'dramaturgs': creating *There is a Light* from complex research data. *Res Involv Engagem*. 2020 Aug 10;6:48. doi: 10.1186/s40900-020-00222-5. PMID: 32789023; PMCID: PMC7418195. Taylor RM, Whelan JS, Gibson F, Morgan S, Fern LA; BRIGHTLIGHT Team; Young Advisory Panel (YAP); Core Consumer Group (CCG) and National Cancer Research Institute Teenage and Young Adult Clinical Studies Group (NCRI TYA CSG). Involving young people in BRIGHTLIGHT from study inception to secondary data analysis: insights from 10 years of user involvement. *Res Involv Engagem*. 2018 Dec 27;4:50. doi: 10.1186/s40900-018-0135-x. PMID: 30607259; PMCID: PMC6307198.

²⁶ Burgers, V. W. G., Dickhout, A., Harthoorn, N. C. G. L., Frissen, S. A. M. M., Noordhoek, M. J., Franssen, S. A., Reuvers, M. J. P., van der Graaf, W. T. A., & Husson, O. (2023). Involving adolescents and young adults (AYA) with an uncertain or poor cancer prognosis as research partners. *Acta Oncologica*, 62(8), 961–968. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0284186X.2023.2238554>.

confidence and empowerment of the participating research partners.²⁷ Beyond proposing new forms of patient involvement, the study by Burgers et al. 2023 also includes a supplementary list of practical tips for researchers and patients developing involvement practices in AYA research, pointing to the first ‘best practices’ in doing and evaluating patient involvement practices, as discussed below. Before turning to evaluation frameworks, this report first gives an overview of types of involvement practices currently present in STRONG AYA.

6.2 Example of involvement practices in STRONG AYA

Varying categorizations or taxonomies of different types of involvement practices (i.e. patient consultation, patient representation, etc.) exist in scholarly literature.²⁸ Oftentimes, taxonomies aim to classify the “degree of influence” of patients on a scale from limited participation to active and extensive patient participation, by which patients take leading roles and executive decisions.²⁹ Particularly relevant in the context of the STRONG AYA project is scholarly work focused on patient involvement in data-intensive health research. Following the work of Katharina Beier and co-authors (Beier et al. 2019), patient involvement or patient participation in data-intensive research can be divided in three overarching levels: consent to research/treatment (which includes creating the patient information on which consent is based); consultation as a basis for shaping research (defining aims and limits by means of surveys/interviews or by different forms of representation, including representation by patient organizations); cooperation of patients as co-researchers in defining aims, design and implementation of research (possibly in all phases of the research process).³⁰ Beier et al.’s tripartite model of consent, consultation and cooperation in data-intensive research health research is underpinned by a broad definition of patient involvement that fits with the variety of practices and tasks that are part of the STRONG AYA consortium. What follows are examples of different types of patient involvement strategies and involvement moments within the STRONG AYA consortium, with examples for each involvement category of “consent”, “consultation” and “cooperation.” This list of involvement practices is not exhaustive but is meant to feed into reflections on evaluating patient involvement in the next sections.

²⁷ Burgers, V. W. G., Dickhout, A., Harthoorn, N. C. G. L., Frissen, S. A. M. M., Noordhoek, M. J., Franssen, S. A., Reuvers, M. J. P., van der Graaf, W. T. A., & Husson, O. (2023). Involving adolescents and young adults (AYA) with an uncertain or poor cancer prognosis as research partners. *Acta Oncologica*, 62(8), 961–968. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0284186X.2023.2238554>.

²⁸ Wait, S., & Nolte, E. (2006). Public involvement policies in health: Exploring their conceptual basis. *Health Economics, Policy and Law*, 1(2), 149–162. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S174413310500112X>.

²⁹ Arnstein, Sherry R. 2007. “A Ladder Of Citizen Participation.” *Journal of the American Institute of Planners*, November. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944366908977225>. Tritter, Jonathan Quetzal, and Alison McCallum. 2006. “The Snakes and Ladders of User Involvement: Moving beyond Arnstein.” *Health Policy* 76 (2): 156–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2005.05.008>.

³⁰ Beier, K., Schweda, M., & Schicktanz, S. (2019). Taking patient involvement seriously: A critical ethical analysis of participatory approaches in data-intensive medical research. *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, 19(1), 90. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-019-0799-7>.

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Figure 1: Types of patient involvement in STRONG AYA

³¹ Re: Consent - At the time of writing this report, only the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI), as one of the STRONG AYA partners, had already obtained ethics approval. At this point, no new or extended requests for patient consent were necessary at NKI, because the STRONG AYA study uses data that is routinely collected in clinical practice and thus available by data desk request from the electronic health record. See D 1.10. Development of a Core Outcome Set (COS) for AYAs with cancer and data collection. "This study protocol assumes standard of care is provided to AYA cancer patients, there is no clinical intervention performed by or within this protocol. Therefore, no informed patient consent is needed to collect the data described in this protocol. (...) As no individual patient

data will be exchanged between institutions, no data transfer agreements or additional patient consent will be needed.” “If or when PRO data beyond the outcomes collected as part of clinical care and previous studies are desired for STRONG AYA in accordance with our finalized COS, a new protocol or amendment (in accordance to IRB guidelines) will be developed.”

<h1 style="margin: 0;">CONSULTATION</h1>	
Patient involvement in the design of patient reporting outcomes measures data collection	Patient involvement in overall consortium work of the STRONG AYA research project
<p>Patients were consulted to inform and guide the process of data collection and creation of a data dashboard. Next to interviewing healthcare professionals, the STRONG AYA consortium conducted qualitative interviews with 27 adolescents and young adults (AYAs) with/who had cancer between the ages of 15-39 years to understand their preferred format of data collection of patient reported outcomes, as well as to understand their views on the design/format/functionality of the reports for the digital dashboard/resource that STRONG AYA aims to develop.³³</p> <p>The results of this interview study provide guidance towards the development of the data collection methods (for example a preference for a mobile app, preference for a questionnaire that takes between 10 and 20 minutes) and dashboard design (preference for graphical/statistical representation of results, for example). Patients were also asked about data sharing preferences: “All AYAs reported that they would be happy for any information they provide about themselves to be shared with clinicians and researchers, if the data is anonymized. Most of the participants interviewed reported being open to share any information about themselves, however a few discussed potential difficulties in sharing information around issues relating to sexual intimacy, relationships, fertility and mental health.”</p>	<p>Patient involvement is an integral part of the ‘stakeholder involvement and engagement’ strategy led within STRONG AYA by the European Cancer Organisation.³⁴ The stakeholder involvement framework includes 1. Stakeholder forum meetings, 2. A STRONG-AYA Stakeholder Board, 3. Stakeholder Surveys, 4. Invitation-only meetings for alignment and best-practice exchange among specifically identified projects, organisations and initiatives. At the time of writing, the first stakeholder forum meeting and stakeholder board meeting have taken place and have been attended, among other stakeholders, by patient representatives and patient advocacy organisations. Hence, patient involvement through the stakeholder program predominantly takes the shape of representation through patient organizations. To reach a representative and diverse sample of patient representatives, ECO draws on its longstanding expertise and established network, including the “Engaged External Consultative Supporters platform.” ECO’s stakeholder engagement activities can include elements of patient involvement but are not exclusively focused on patient involvement. Within STRONG AYA, Youth Cancer Europe is leading on patient involvement.</p>
Patient involvement in overall governance of STRONG AYA	Patient involvement in informing ethical issue mapping
<p>As part of the governance of the STRONG AYA research consortium, a Patient Advisory Board (PAB) consisting of 6 individuals with lived experience of cancer in the AYA age group has been established. This board provides non-binding consultation, guidance and recommendations to members of the consortium. The work contributed by members of the PAB is envisioned to be used in project planning, outputs, and deliverables. PAB members may be expected to complete tasks including, but not limited to reviewing the work of individual WPs and flagging any incorrect information or inconsistencies in the meeting minutes or agendas. Members of the PAB receive a monetary compensation for their work.³⁶ Recruitment of PAB members has been carried out with the aim of maximizing diverse knowledge, experience and expertise while employing principles of Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI).^[1] By paying specific attention to EDI in the selection of the PAB, this board will aid the STRONG AYA consortium in understanding the challenges and barriers faced by the vulnerable and marginalized groups of cancer patient communities in order to promote equity and inclusion.</p>	<p>STRONG AYA’s ‘stakeholder involvement and engagement’ strategy supports a bottom-up approach to ethical analysis within the consortium. Stakeholder forum meetings, Stakeholder Board meetings and stakeholder surveys are envisioned as tools to inquire with patients and patient organisations (as well as other stakeholders) about which ethical issues are pressing and relevant for people with lived experience of cancer during the AYA age. The consortium takes this patient-informed approach to ethics to avoid assuming which ethical issues are salient to patients. By using the stakeholder program, patient involvement here predominantly takes the shape of representation through patient organizations.</p>

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Figure 2: types of patient involvement in STRONG AYA, continued

6.3 Frameworks for improving and evaluating patient involvement in (AYA cancer) research

In the previous section we have listed examples of patient involvement practices currently part of the STRONG AYA project. These practices abide by general guidelines set in the STRONG-AYA information governance and ethics framework.³⁵ In past decades, patient organizations have rallied for formulating and monitoring specific criteria for the evaluation of patient involvement practices. The European Patient Forum, for example, reflecting on HORIZON EUROPE, has called for “clear criteria for meaningful patient involvement in calls to be developed together with patient organisations, to avoid researchers treating ‘patient involvement’ as a tick-box exercise as they still too often do, and to reward those projects that practice genuine co-creation and co-production.”³⁶

The evaluation of involvement practices is a complex issue: a wide variety of frameworks and guidelines exist in academic and professional literature, with differing approaches and focus.³⁷ A 2019 systematic review (Greenhalgh et al. 2019) of tools, frameworks, benchmarks, guidelines and checklists for patient involvement in research found 56 relevant frameworks. Analysing these frameworks for involvement practices, Greenhalgh et al. distinguished five main types: power-focused frameworks, priority-setting frameworks, study-focused frameworks, report-focused frameworks and partnership-focused frameworks. Recently, two guidelines specifically centred on improving patient involvement in AYA research have been published.³⁸ Burgers et al. (2022) developed a list of tips for the involvement of patients as research partners in the context of a research that conducted qualitative interviews with AYA patients with uncertain and/or poor cancer prognosis (UPCP) to better understand their daily life challenges, coping, and healthcare needs.³⁹

³² Re: patient involvement in PROM design, see D1.1. Digital technology requirements, Report including specification for digital technology selection, adaptation and/or development.

³³ Re: patient involvement in overall consortium work, see D 4.1 Stakeholder involvement and engagement plan.

³⁴ Re: patient involvement in overall governance, see D4.2 Bylaws of the Patient Advisory Board (PAB). at 25EU/hour but are free to opt out from any compensation. Individual contracts will be drafted in agreement with YCE, the lead beneficiary who will remunerate PAB members’ time (up to 1,500EU per member for the duration of the project). In case members of the PAB will be asked to participate in any in-person activities or General Assembly, YCE may compensate up to 8 hours per day of attendance. See also Monge-Montero, C., O’Callaghan, S., Rizvi, K., Kosir, U., & Girbu, V. (2023). *Recommendations for Equitable, Diverse, and Inclusive Cancer Care in Europe*. Youth Cancer Europe. European Commission co-funded project: EU-CAYAS-NET EU4H-2021-PJ-04101056918. <https://www.youthcancereurope.org/the-european-network-of-youth-cancer-survivors-launches-its-recommendations-for-equitable-diverse-and-inclusive-cancer-care-in-europe>.

³⁵ D2.2. STRONG-AYA information governance and ethics framework.

³⁶ *Horizon Europe must invest more in health to support high-quality, accessible and equitable health systems*. (2018). European Patients Forum. <https://www.eu-patient.eu/news/latest-epf-news/2018/horizon-europe-must-invest-more-in-health-to-support-high-quality-accessible-and-equitable-health-systems/>.

³⁷ Greenhalgh, T., Hinton, L., Finlay, T., Macfarlane, A., Fahy, N., Clyde, B., & Chant, A. (2019). Frameworks for supporting patient and public involvement in research: Systematic review and co-design pilot. *Health Expectations*, 22(4), 785–801. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.12888>.

³⁸ van Ham, C. R., Burgers, V. W. G., Sleeman, S. H. E., Dickhout, A., Harthoorn, N. C. G. L., Manten-Horst, E., van Eenbergen, M. C., & Husson, O. (2022). A qualitative study on the involvement of adolescents and young adults (AYAs) with cancer during multiple research phases: “Plan, structure, and discuss.” *Research Involvement and Engagement*, 8(1), 30. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40900-022-00362-w>. Oveisi, N., Cheng, V., Taylor, D., Bechthold, H., Barnes, M., Jansen, N., McTaggart-Cowan, H., Brotto, L. A., Peacock, S., Hanley, G. E., Gill, S., Rayar, M., Srikanthan, A., & De Vera, M. A. (2024). Meaningful Patient Engagement in Adolescent and Young Adult (AYA) Cancer Research: A Framework for Qualitative Studies. *Current Oncology*, 31(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/curroncol31040128>.

³⁹ Burgers, V. W. G., Dickhout, A., Harthoorn, N. C. G. L., Frissen, S. A. M. M., Noordhoek, M. J., Franssen, S. A., Reuvers, M. J. P., van der Graaf, W. T. A., & Husson, O. (2023). Involving adolescents and young adults (AYA) with an uncertain or poor cancer prognosis as research partners. *Acta Oncologica*, 62(8), 961–968. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0284186X.2023.2238554>.

Oveisi et al. (2024) published a framework for patient research partners (PRPs) in the context of a research that employs qualitative methods (focus groups) to explore the impacts of cancer diagnosis and treatment on the sexual and reproductive health of AYA cancer patients [figure 3].⁴⁰

Table 1. Collaborative and iterative framework for meaningful patient engagement in adolescent and young adult (AYA) cancer qualitative research.

Overarching Principles		Description
Safety		Ensuring that AYA cancer PRPs feel physically and emotionally safe throughout the research process
Flexibility		Providing space for the diverse needs and lifestyles of AYA cancer PRPs in their contribution to the research study
Sensitivity		Approaching AYA cancer PRPs with empathy and awareness, while thoroughly integrating moments of acknowledgement and support systems
Study Phase	Consideration (c)/Task (t)	Points
Across all study phases	Collaboration (c)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What does “collaboration” mean to the research team? - What is the role of PRPs in the research team/research study?
	Iteration (c)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can flexibility be built into the research study to allow for changes based on PRPs’ inputs? In which study phase(s) would this be feasible? - Are there opportunities for conversations on iterations within the research study?
	Communication (c)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Who will be the researcher(s) communicating with PRP(s)? - What method of communication (e.g., email, text messages, or team management applications) will be used?
	Equity, diversity, and inclusion (c)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What steps have the research team taken to ensure representation of PRPs? - Has there been reflection on and the unlearning of the research team’s internal biases? - Are there safety measures in place to ensure that PRPs feel supported and seen?
Developing the study	Planning for engagement with PRPs (t)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How will PRPs be recruited? - How many PRPs will be part of the team and what is their level of involvement?
	Funding PRPs (c, t)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Have PRPs been listed as research team members on grant applications and provided opportunities for feedback? - Are there systems in place to alleviate the burden of funding applications on PRPs (e.g., assistance for preparing letters of support and CV development, etc.)? - How will PRPs be compensated for their involvement (e.g., honorariums)?
	Integrating PRPs’ perspectives (t)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How will the research study integrate PRPs’ experience and knowledge? - Are there opportunities for redefining gaps from PRPs’ input?
Conducting the study	Developing study materials (t)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are study materials co-created with PRPs? - Do PRPs have opportunities to lead aspects of the study?
	Recruiting participants (t)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are recruitment strategies co-created with PRPs? - Are PRPs involved in recruitment?
	Collecting data (t)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How have PRPs taken an active role during data collection (e.g., co-facilitator, moderator, etc.)? - Are there opportunities for revising data collection protocols according to PRPs’ input?
	Analyzing data (t)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are PRPs involved in data analysis? - Are PRPs provided with support (e.g., with research jargon and training on methods) to facilitate involvement in data analysis?
Translating the study	Ownership of study materials (t)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are PRPs listed as co-investigators/co-authors on study material? - Are PRPs supported in study-related pursuits?
	Maximizing KT (t)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How will KT integrate PRP experience and knowledge? - Are PRP networks leveraged for KT?

Figure 3: Collaborative and iterative framework for meaningful patient engagement in adolescent and young adult (AYA) cancer qualitative research. Developed by and reproduced from Oveisi et al. 2024⁴¹

The studies of Burgers et al. 2022 and Oveisi et al. 2024 are close to what Greenhalgh et al. have typified as “study-focused” frameworks for evaluating involvement practices, whereby researchers distinguish different phases in a research project linked to various potential involvement challenges and issues. Both guidelines focus on patients as research partners - i.e. on consultation and cooperation by means

⁴⁰ Oveisi, N., Cheng, V., Taylor, D., Bechthold, H., Barnes, M., Jansen, N., McTaggart-Cowan, H., Brotto, L. A., Peacock, S., Hanley, G. E., Gill, S., Rayar, M., Srikanthan, A., & De Vera, M. A. (2024). Meaningful Patient Engagement in Adolescent and Young Adult (AYA) Cancer Research: A Framework for Qualitative Studies. *Current Oncology*, 31(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/curroncol31040128>.

⁴¹ Oveisi, N., Cheng, V., Taylor, D., Bechthold, H., Barnes, M., Jansen, N., McTaggart-Cowan, H., Brotto, L. A., Peacock, S., Hanley, G. E., Gill, S., Rayar, M., Srikanthan, A., & De Vera, M. A. (2024). Meaningful Patient Engagement in Adolescent and Young Adult (AYA) Cancer Research: A Framework for Qualitative Studies. *Current Oncology*, 31(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/curroncol31040128>.

of direct involvement of individual patients. Not part of the focus of these AYA guidelines are involvement through patient representative organizations, the role of patients in governance of research consortia, as well as procedures of patient consent. As Greenhalgh et al. 2019 have emphasized, frameworks for evaluating patient involvement developed in the context of one research may not be (entirely) fitting for other contexts. Research projects may need to develop a tailor-made evaluation framework based, for example, on a participatory workshop in which patients are involved in designing the evaluation criteria and framework for patient involvement practices.⁴² In the next section, we list issues related to patient involvement and evaluation of involvement that deserve special attention in the context of the STRONG AYA project.

7 Expanding current frameworks for evaluating patient involvement to fit with STRONG AYA

As outlined above, frameworks for evaluating patient involvement in the domain of AYA care and research are still rare (our research turned up two guidelines, Burgers et al. 2022 & Oveisi et al. 2024) and need to be adapted to the variety of involvement practices that are part of the STRONG AYA consortium. Based on analysis of AYA research literature, as well as experience by consortium members, particularly within the European Cancer Organisation and Youth Cancer Europe, below is a non-exhaustive list of aspects that deserve further attention in relation to improving and monitoring the quality of involvement practices in AYA work.

7.1 Adequate structures for financially compensating AYA involvement work

Within STRONG AYA, Youth Cancer Europe has set up platforms for patient involvement, including a Patient Advisory Board. In these various tasks, financial compensation for work by patient advocates is outlined, i.e. the process is made transparent and sets expectations of how much time they can devote.⁴³ However, even when financial compensation is secured for patient involvement work, current structures and mechanisms for compensation might not fit the financial circumstances in which AYA patients find themselves. For example, adolescents and young adults in treatment or off treatment may be receiving disability pay, which can conflict with the financial payments they receive because of involvement work. AYAs will need access to experts with knowledge of these financial regulations in their home country. At present, EU research projects are often not equipped with adequate consultation on this issue.

⁴² "Appendix S2: Facilitator notes for PPI build-your-own-framework workshop." in Greenhalgh, Trisha, Lisa Hinton, Teresa Finlay, Alastair Macfarlane, Nick Fahy, Ben Clyde, and Alan Chant. 2019. "Frameworks for Supporting Patient and Public Involvement in Research: Systematic Review and Co-Design Pilot." *Health Expectations* 22 (4): 785–801. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.12888>.

⁴³ D4.2. Bylaws of the Patient Advisory Board (PAB) (M6): Terms of reference and principles for the selection of participants, operation and governance of the PAB. "All members of the PAB will be offered monetary compensation for their time and work at 25EU/hour but are free to opt out from any compensation. Individual contracts will be drafted in agreement with YCE, the lead beneficiary who will remunerate PAB members' time (up to 1,500EU per member for the duration of the project). In case members of the PAB will be asked to participate in any in-person activities or General Assembly, YCE may compensate up to 8 hours per day of attendance. Any travel arrangements will need to be agreed upon with the entire Consortium. In order to provide adequate justification and eligibility of any corresponding costs, PAB members will have the responsibility of keeping their own record of time spent on the project (with guidance from the PAB secretariat). The PAB secretariat will take responsibility to check all correspondence between the time declared by the PAB members and their actual participation in the project."

7.2 Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) in AYA involvement work

Researchers have pointed to the barriers and burdens faced by marginalised AYA patients in participating in patient representation and involvement practices.⁴⁴ To realise the existing recommendations and expertise with EDI in AYA care, adequate compensation is vital, but not enough. Improving the funding of participation of professionals with EDI expertise is necessary, as well as supporting the participation of marginalised groups within which we might be able to identify AYAs with lived experience that can enhance inclusivity in practice, particularly to promote EDI for racial and ethnic minority AYAs.⁴⁵ EDI criteria are already part of STRONG AYA's involvement practices, for example in the recruitment process for the Patient Advisory Board.⁴⁶ Going forward, it is important to employ similar EDI criteria and standards for AYA cancer research teams as well. By ensuring diversity across all facets of the research process, EDI in patient involvement can be more readily and satisfactorily accomplished. Moreover, recent research into the attitudes toward EDI in the AYA population has showed that diversity work should include categories beyond gender, race and ethnicity, such e.g. disability and neurodiversity.⁴⁷

7.3 Adequate patient representation

As mentioned during the 2023 STRONG AYA stakeholder forum, “adequate patient representation” is important, as patient involvement in larger research consortiums often takes the shape of consultation through patient representatives as well as professionals working at patient advocacy organizations.⁴⁸ The evaluation of patient representation practices is a complex and contested issue: who is regarded as the proper representative at specific involvement moments in health research is context-dependent and contingent on shifting values and perspectives about the aims of representation work.⁴⁹ To be able to do representation work, for example as a person with lived experience of AYA, requires substantial levels of knowledge, adaptive skills (to adjust to variable demands by a diverse consortium), free time, financial

⁴⁴ Cheung, C. K., Tucker-Seeley, R., Davies, S., Gilman, M., Miller, K. A., Lopes, G., Betz, G. D., Katerere-Virima, T., Helbling, L. E., Thomas, B. N., & Lewis, M. A. (2021). A call to action: Antiracist patient engagement in adolescent and young adult oncology research and advocacy. *Future Oncology*, 17(28), 3743–3756. <https://doi.org/10.2217/fon-2020-1213>. Cheung, C. K., Miller, K. A., Goings, T. C., Thomas, B. N., Lee, H., Brandon, R. E., Katerere-Virima, T., Helbling, L. E., Causadias, J. M., Roth, M. E., Berthaud, F. M., Jones, L. P., Ross, V. A., Betz, G. D., Simmons, C. D., Carter, J., Davies, S. J., Gilman, M. L., Lewis, M. A., ... Tucker-Seeley, R. D. (2024). BIPOC Experiences of (anti-)Racist Patient Engagement in Adolescent and Young Adult Oncology Research: An Electronic Delphi Study. *Future Oncology*, 20(9), 547–561. <https://doi.org/10.2217/fon-2023-0771>.

⁴⁵ Cheung, C. K., Tucker-Seeley, R., Davies, S., Gilman, M., Miller, K. A., Lopes, G., Betz, G. D., Katerere-Virima, T., Helbling, L. E., Thomas, B. N., & Lewis, M. A. (2021). A call to action: Antiracist patient engagement in adolescent and young adult oncology research and advocacy. *Future Oncology*, 17(28), 3743–3756. <https://doi.org/10.2217/fon-2020-1213>.

⁴⁶ D. 4.2 Bylaws of the Patient Advisory Board (PAB). Mentions the selection criteria for PAB members, with the aim of maximizing diverse knowledge, experience and expertise while employing principles of Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI). “The EDI principles consider diversity of thought, experience, expertise, geographical representation, gender identity, educational status, health status and disability as essential aspects of delivering work fit-for-purpose of this multinational project.”

⁴⁷ Monge-Montero, Carmen, Stewart O’Callaghan, Katie Rizvi, Urska Kosir, and Victor Girbu. 2023. “Recommendations for Equitable, Diverse, and Inclusive Cancer Care in Europe.” Yout Cancer Europe. European Commission co-funded project: EU-CAYAS-NET EU4H-2021-PJ-04101056918. <https://www.youthcancereurope.org/the-european-network-of-youth-cancer-survivors-launches-its-recommendations-for-equitable-diverse-and-inclusive-cancer-care-in-europe/>.

⁴⁸ L’Hôte, M., Lorenzo i Sunyer, N., & Couespel, N. (2024). Caught in the Middle: Identifying Gaps for Adolescents and Young Adults (AYAs) with Cancer. European Cancer Organisation. <https://www.europecancer.org/resources/publications/reports/identifying-gaps-adolescents-young-adults-ayas-cancer.html>

⁴⁹ Halloy, Arnaud, Emmanuelle Simon, and Fabienne Hejoaka. 2023. “Defining Patient’s Experiential Knowledge: Who, What and How Patients Know. A Narrative Critical Review.” *Sociology of Health & Illness* 45 (2): 405–22. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9566.13588>. Mankell, Anna, and Mio Fredriksson. 2021. “Federative Patient Organizations in a Decentralized Health-Care System: A Challenge for Representation?” *Health* 25 (6): 722–38. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1363459320912807>.

resources and willpower.⁵⁰ This set of requirements often means that a small group of available, trained and experienced patients becomes frequently approached by stakeholders and turn into recurrent representatives or 'expert patients'.⁵¹ In past years, with increasing demands for patient representation practices, patient organisations have become important intermediaries for representation.⁵² They have become endowed with increasing responsibilities in recruiting fitting representatives, ensuring diversity through recruiting a broad group of representatives, facilitating training of representatives and preventing forms of fatigue and bias within the pool of representatives. To play this intermediary role, patient organisations should be facilitated and financially supported, for example by providing structural funding (beyond project-based funding) to build up a continuous training program for AYA cancer patient representatives.

7.4 Patient involvement with secondary use of data in data-intensive health research

Research on AYA-cancer issues in STRONG AYA depends on the ability to pool personal health data from different countries to perform retrospective studies, i.e. the 'secondary use' of personal health data for research. At present, ethical use of secondary data in STRONG AYA is ensured through existing national legislations regarding patient consent and GDPR. At the same time, a recent EU-proposal for the European Health Data space proposes new legislation that would increase secondary data use to facilitate research.⁵³ Within this emerging legislation, the role of patient involvement is left undefined. While patient control is explicitly mentioned for primary use of healthcare data, the EHDS is not specific about how and what type of information about secondary use of data should be provided to patients, nor how patients can partake in governance or development practices.⁵⁴ The STRONG AYA project has developed efforts to inquire into AYA patients' attitudes towards data protection (see section on consultation). Moreover, the consortium can draw on recent studies about health data sharing attitudes towards secondary use of data, which show that patients' approval of secondary data use is dependent on context and purpose of use and type of user.⁵⁵

⁵⁰ Egger, Claudia, and Olga Zvonareva. 2024. "Knowledge-Based Representation: Patient Engagement in Drug Development." *Health Expectations* 27 (1): e13912. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.13912>.

⁵¹ Pols, Jeannette. 2014. "Knowing Patients: Turning Patient Knowledge into Science." *Science, Technology, & Human Values* 39 (1): 73–97. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243913504306>.

⁵² Moreira, Tiago. 2015. "Understanding the Role of Patient Organizations in Health Technology Assessment." *Health Expectations* 18 (6): 3349–57. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.12325>.

⁵³ European Commission. Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the European Health Data Space. 3 May 2022. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:dbfd8974-cb79-11ec-b6f4-01aa75ed71a1.000102/DOC_1&format=PDF.

⁵⁴ Member states are requested to develop health data access bodies (HDABs, a public sector body) to create a governance structure that facilitates secondary use. Saelaert, Marlies, Louise Mathieu, Wannes Van Hoof, and Brecht Devleeschauwer. 2023. "Expanding Citizen Engagement in the Secondary Use of Health Data: An Opportunity for National Health Data Access Bodies to Realise the Intentions of the European Health Data Space." *Archives of Public Health* 81 (1): 168. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13690-023-01182-4>.

⁵⁵ A 2024 systematic review of health data sharing attitudes found more than a dozen studies examining attitudes towards sharing personal health data and information. Studies found a higher intention to share data for secondary use correlated with variables, younger age, female gender, higher education level, health care occupation, being white and region of residence (Europe and Middle East were more willing than North Americans and Asians). Other studies found that younger patients were more uncomfortable than older patients to share data. Generally, for many patients, sharing secondary data was conditional upon specific use purposes and specific users, being informed, having a choice, perceived use, trust in data protection, use by a trustworthy actor, such as a government agency or public institution. Cascini, Fidelia, Ana Pantovic, Yazan A. Al-Ajlouni, Valeria Puleo, Lucia De Maio, and Walter Ricciardi. 2024. "Health Data Sharing Attitudes towards Primary and Secondary Use of Data: A Systematic Review." *eClinicalMedicine* 71 (May). <https://doi.org/10.1016/i.eclinm.2024.102551>.

However, as researchers have emphasized, experiments with new ways of involving citizens and patients with the issue of secondary health data are necessary.⁵⁶

7.5 Understanding patient attitudes towards patient involvement work in the AYA cancer field

Research on (AYA cancer) patient attitudes towards involvement in research practices has shown that attitudes vary according to different age groups. Adolescents are found to want to take a less proactive and involved role compared to older (20+) patients.⁵⁷ Other variables may also be important in attitudes towards patient involvement, such as gender, income, education level, having a family. While there is research into participation attitudes of patients as research subjects, including reasons of response or non-response by AYA patients to invitations to enrol in PRO-studies, this research does not address the topic of patient involvement in research.⁵⁸ More research is necessary to understand motivations for – and attitudes towards – patient involvement on the part of patients. Future research should also include a study into the way patients are informed about the value of patient involvement (before participating) as well as methods of reflection and evaluation with patients after involvement practices.

8 Conclusion

This report has provided a targeted literature review of patient involvement practices and patient involvement evaluation practices focused on the field of AYA cancer research. In recent years, efforts to involve patients in AYA research have been introduced within the AYA population, though the number of initiatives is still relatively small. Despite the widespread calls for involvement practices, implementation, monitoring and evaluation practices for AYA participation are lacking in many European countries. There are currently no European standards for involvement practices with AYAs with lived experience and context-dependent policies and best practices should be developed. This report has offered a preliminary mapping of the type of patient involvement practices that are part of the STRONG AYA project, showing examples of ‘consent’, ‘consultation’ and ‘cooperation’ practices. The report has also discussed the topic of evaluation frameworks for patient involvement in relation to STRONG AYA’s involvement efforts. A wide variety of frameworks and guidelines exist in academic and professional literature, with differing approaches and focus. Recently, two guidelines specifically centered on improving patient involvement in AYA research have been published. The report ends with recommendations for improving evaluation frameworks for patient involvement in the context of research projects such as STRONG AYA.

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⁵⁶ Saelaert, Marlies, Louise Mathieu, Wannes Van Hoof, and Brecht Devleeschauwer. 2023. “Expanding Citizen Engagement in the Secondary Use of Health Data: An Opportunity for National Health Data Access Bodies to Realise the Intentions of the European Health Data Space.” *Archives of Public Health* 81 (1): 168. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13690-023-01182-4>.

⁵⁷ Siembida, E. J., Kadan-Lottick, N. S., Moss, K., & Bellizzi, K. M. (2018). Adolescent cancer patients’ perceived quality of cancer care: The roles of patient engagement and supporting independence. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 101(9), 1683–1689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2018.04.002>

⁵⁸ Vlooswijk, Carla, Lonneke V. van de Poll-Franse, Silvie H. M. Janssen, Esther Derksen, Milou J. P. Reuvers, Rhodé Bijlsma, Suzanne E. J. Kaal, et al. 2022. “Recruiting Adolescent and Young Adult Cancer Survivors for Patient-Reported Outcome Research: Experiences and Sample Characteristics of the SURVAYA Study.” *Current Oncology* 29 (8): 5407–25. <https://doi.org/10.3390/curroncol29080428>.

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